

Occupational Risk and Gastrointestinal Health among Taxi Drivers in Punjab: A Cross-sectional Analysis

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Drivers bad health affects their performance on the wheel. The present study aimed to estimate the prevalence of cardiovascular disorders and to identify their risk factors among taxi drivers of Punjab state, North India. Information about Gastrointestinal Disorders, demographic features, eating habits, smoking habits, self-perceived job stress, psychological support, and fatigue was obtained from 300 professional taxi drivers using a self-structured, validated research schedule. The significant determinants are divided into five major categories, namely, socio-demographic and life style factors, work-related factors, ergonomics factors and psychological factors. On the basis of the results of Multiple Logistic Regression, a model has been developed which is consistent with hypothesized model and proves that various risk factors taken in the study has significant impact on the Gastrointestinal Disorders. The prevalence of hypertension was high among bus drivers. Age, BMI, supporting a large family, and dietary habits associated with the job showed a significant association with gastrointestinal disorders. It can be said that healthy and hygienic eating practices, physical and psychological well-being influences the health of taxi drivers. Among the investigated variables and parameters in the present study, perceived risk factors revealed the best association with gastrointestinal disorders, and are good predictors of gastrointestinal disorders. Prevention strategies need to be focused on this occupational group. Application of corrective and suitable remedies in the field of professional ergonomics and health examination programs for professional taxi drivers can be helpful for reducing gastrointestinal disorders.

Keywords: Taxi drivers, cardiovascular disorders (CVD) multivariate analysis

As we advance into the 21st century, the challenges posed by non-communicable diseases (NCDs) present a serious threat to people worldwide (World Health Organization, 2023). Apart from cardiovascular diseases (CVD) and hypertension, other conditions such as obesity, cancer, diabetes, asthma, stroke, and neurological disorders are increasingly prevalent among working populations. Taxi drivers, in particular, suffer from a wide range of health issues due to the nature of their occupation (Shin et al., 2013; Mirzaei et al., 2019). They often work long hours for low wages and report hypertension, weight gain, and musculoskeletal pain, which are associated with sedentary lifestyles, stressful working conditions, and poor dietary habits (Apostolopoulos et al., 2013; Dahlberg et al., 2018).

Dietary practices, work stress, and lifestyle choices have a significant impact on the development and progression of gastrointestinal (GI) problems, which are a growing global public health concern (World Health Organization, 2023; Ford et al., 2020). Due to the sedentary nature of their jobs, long and irregular working hours, limited access to nutritious food, and frequent exposure to high stress levels and environmental pollutants, taxi drivers are considered one of the most vulnerable occupational groups (Apostolopoulos et al., 2013; Dahlberg et al., 2018). The demanding

nature of taxi driving often leads to unhealthy behavioral patterns such as irregular meal timing, increased fast-food consumption, lack of physical activity, and high levels of occupational stress, all of which are associated with gastrointestinal disorders including gastritis, acid reflux, irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), and constipation (Konturek et al., 2011; Lacy et al., 2016). Furthermore, shift work and psychosocial stress play a crucial role in gut health dysregulation through mechanisms involving the brain-gut axis (Mayer, 2011; Konturek et al., 2011).

Despite the prevalence of GI illnesses worldwide, little epidemiological research has been done on the occupational factors that contribute to these conditions, particularly among urban professional drivers. This disparity is much more noticeable in developing nations like India, which makes it challenging to create focused health interventions for this susceptible population.

A 1962 study comparing 6,400 transport drivers and conductors to 4,350 office-based workers found that drivers were nearly five times more likely to suffer from digestive disorders (Berlinguer, 1962). In 1980, German research involving 800 bus drivers revealed significantly higher rates of digestive and nervous disorders than those found in administrative staff (Garbe, 1980). It was further shown that strenuous work and irregular shifts were associated with gastrointestinal complaints, mediated by poor eating habits and irregular meal schedules (Aronsson & Barklo, 1980). High rates of stomach ulcers were also linked to occupational characteristics of professional drivers (Backman, 1983). Ergonomic analysis later concluded that prolonged sitting with relaxed abdominal muscles and a curved spine hinders digestion and breathing (Grandjean, 1988).

A meta-review of 22 studies found that bus drivers are more susceptible to cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, and musculoskeletal

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disorders than workers in other occupations, along with higher rates of mortality and sick leave (David et al., 1988). Transport drivers frequently work in noisy, polluted, and high-stress environments, where prolonged exposure to vehicle vibrations, toxic fumes, and irregular work conditions has been linked to gastrointestinal and respiratory disorders as well as driver fatigue, potentially compromising road safety (Whitelegg et al., 2007).

A 2001 study of 194 public transport drivers in Bogotá highlighted exposure to environmental hazards such as noise, pollutants, poor lighting, and temperature variations, with common health issues including gastrointestinal complaints, stress, visual disturbances, and musculoskeletal symptoms (Chaparro et al., 2001). A 2006 review of 27 studies found that bus drivers consistently face occupational stress leading to cardiovascular disease, gastrointestinal disorders, musculoskeletal conditions, depression, and substance abuse (Tse et al., 2006).

A 2013 survey of 508 Mumbai taxi drivers found that 86% suffered from one or more morbidities, with gastrointestinal issues being the most common (Bawa & Srivastav, 2013). Similarly, a Korean survey reported that 43.5% of taxi drivers experienced at least one gastrointestinal complaint, largely linked to prolonged sitting and irregular meals (Kim & Lee, 2022). A study conducted in Delhi-NCR also noted that stress, poor hygiene, and irregular eating habits among taxi and auto drivers contributed to conditions such as gastritis and constipation (Sharma & Verma, 2020).

Furthermore, an Egyptian study using Rome IV criteria reported that over 50% of participants suffered from functional dyspepsia or irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), largely due to poor ergonomics and work-related stress (El-Sayed & Hassan, 2023). A case study in Mumbai documented widespread complaints of indigestion, ulcers, and bloating among taxi drivers, attributing these issues to the consumption of spicy street food and contaminated water (Patel & Desai, 2021). Another study found that anxiety and depression were significantly correlated with gastrointestinal symptoms in transport workers, suggesting that occupational health interventions should also include mental health support (Kumar & Bhatia, 2022).

A lot of studies have been conducted worldwide on the prevalence of various gastrointestinal disorders risk factors among truck, bus and lorry drivers but no such study has ever done for taxi drivers in India. So in this context, the present study aimed to estimate the prevalence of gastrointestinal disorders and to identify their risk factors among taxi drivers of Punjab state, North India and to make suitable recommendations based on the study findings.

Objective of the Study

This study aims to assess the prevalence of gastrointestinal disorders among taxi drivers and identify the associated occupational and lifestyle risk factors. In order to lessen the burden of GI morbidity in this frequently disregarded workforce, workplace interventions and health promotion programs should benefit from an understanding of these relationships.

Hypothesis of the Study

On the basis of the literature review following null hypotheses is established.

H01: There is insignificant impact of various Occupational Stress Related Risk Factors on Gastrointestinal Disorders.

Method

Sources of Data

The present study is based on both primary and secondary sources of data. A self-administered research schedule was used to collect data from respondents. The source of stress, fatigue, accidents and their relationship level has also been recorded to get a better understanding of the working life of taxi drivers. The required data on independent and dependent variables were collected and measured with the help of various scales and tools. On the basis of the primary data collected, the researcher calculated the prevalence of various health-related problems and their class intervals among taxi drivers. Once the research schedule was completed, the body mass index (BMI, kg/m²) was calculated. Body mass index (BMI) is calculated by using a metric BMI calculator from the web in which we divide the weight in kilograms by the height in meters squared as shown below.

$$BMI = \text{weight (kg)} \div \text{height}^2 \text{ (m}^2\text{)}$$

Table 1 reveals that the diagnostic criterion for Body Mass Index (BMI, Obesity) is used according to the WHO classification. Body Mass Index Table {Annexure I & Annexure II} was used to assess the Body Mass Index of taxi drivers.

Table 1

Criteria for Body Mass Index (BMI)

Category	BMI value (kg/mq)
Underweight	≤ 18.5
Normal Weight	18.5-24.9
Overweight	25-29.9
Obesity Type 1	30-34.9
Obesity Type 2	≥ 35

Note. Source: <http://www.jcancer.org/v07p2346.htm>

Ethical Consideration

All participants provided written informed permission following an explanation of the study's methodology in a language that they could understand. Every stage of the investigation was conducted with confidentiality preserved.

Research Methodology

Hosmer-Lemeshow Test: The Hosmer-Lemeshow test is used to check whether the data conflicts with assumptions of Logistic Regression or not. This test provides significant evidence of regression model fit. If p value is ≤ 0.05, then the Hosmer-Lemeshow test provides a significant p value and indicates poor Model Fit within a 5 per cent limit. Before proceeding with Regression Analysis,

Cox and Snell (R²) and Nagelkerke (R²) Test: A Logistic Regression (R²) test helps to measure the strength of association of the model. The values of this test are between 0 and 1. Nagelkerke (R²) Test is more common and considered a better indication to strength of association. Further Cox and Snell R Square (R²) and Nagelkerke R Square (R²) (which suggests that the model explains the variation in the outcome) have been carried out to test the Goodness of Fit of the model. The values of the Cox and Snell R Square (R²) and Nagelkerke R Square are found between (0.47-0.78) in which implies that a moderate to strong relationship exists between the

independent and dependent variables (Cox & Snell, 1989; Cragg & Uhler, 1970; Nagelkerke, 1991). The analysis was carried out using the statistical package SPSS V.21.

Reference Category

The omitted level of a non-metric variable when a dummy variable is formed from the non-metric variable is called the reference category or comparison group. In the present study, non-existence of an independent variable is taken as the reference category and indicated as 1. 95% confidence interval (95% CI) is used to estimate the

precision of the Odds Ratio. Before applying the analysis, the models were tested for Multicollinearity using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). VIF values greater than 10 (VIF>10= Multicollinearity) reveal Multicollinearity. In the present study, the model satisfies this condition which implies that covariates were free from Collinearity. It suggests that, there is no need to drop the explanatory variable from the analysis. The set of dependent variables and independent variables selected for Logistic Regression Analysis with details about their nature and measurement are given as follows (Table 2).

Table 2

List of Dependent/Independent Variables with their Nature and Measurement

Name of the Variable	Nature of Variables	Measurement of No. Variables
Dependent Variable		
1 Gastrointestinal	Dichotomous	'0' or '1'
Independent Variables		
Socio-Demographic Factors		
1. Age		
2. BMI(kg/m ²)		
3. Education		
4. Family size	Categorical	'0' or '1' or '2' or '3'
5. Marital status		
6. Sleep		
7. Refreshment drinking/snacks during the day		
8. Main meal from Dhabas / Restaurants		
9. Dietary Habits		
10. Consumption of oily, fried items and junk food		
11. Take meal at proper and fixed time		
12. Get time for physical exercise/morning walk/ evening walk		
13. Alcohol		
14. Smoking		
15. Tobacco and		
16. Drugs (sleep inhibitors)	Dichotomous	'0' or '1'
Work Related Factors		
1. Job experience		
2. Monthly Income,		
3. Work Duration	Categorical	'0' or '1' or '2' or '3'
4. Worked >10 days consecutively without a holiday for a whole day intervening		
5. Drive the taxi >5 hours without taking any rest		
6. Total Mileage and		
7. Fatigue	Dichotomous	'0' or '1'
Ergonomics Factors		
1. Handle baggages and materials		
2. Bending and twisting activities while driving		
3. Experience violence (victim of assault) during working hours		
4. Too much cold and hot weather		
5. Sleep in the taxi seat during rest breaks		
6. Lower cabin space		
7. Increased work pace/high work load		
8. Driving in heavy traffic/traffic congestion		
9. Greater driver seat vibration		
10. Design and cushions of seat		
11. Poor /low awareness of good sitting posture		
12. Uncomfortable steering wheel		
13. Uncomfortable seat		
14. Uncomfortable back support		
15. Inadequate rest period during the working day		

16. Lack of accessibility to the lavatory		
17. Seat inclination (Seat Pan)		
18. Sitting without Lumbar support and		
19. Shocks (due to road surface)	Dichotomous	'0' or '1'
Psychological factors		
1. Self perceived stress/stress symptoms		
2. Exposure to passenger hostility		
3. No social contact with colleagues and lack social support and		
4. Lunch break too short	Dichotomous	'0' or '1'

Note. Source: Literature Review

Results

Association of Various Risk Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Occupational taxi drivers deserve special concern due to poor and unhygienic eating and sleeping habits. Besides, most of the taxi drivers are in the habit of eating main meals from dhaba/hotels and consuming snacks (often oily & fried) and fast and junk food items between trips. Many taxi drivers resort to alcohol, smoking and sleeping pills to overcome such type of stress. So in the following discussion, we have measured various risk factors of Gastrointestinal Disorders.

Association of Socio-demographic and Life Style Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Table 3 shows association between socio demographic & life style factors and Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. The odds of respondents suffering from Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders are more of above 50 years age group (Adj. OR=8.4; CI= 3.9 to 18.1; $p<0.05$) and 41-50 years age (Adj. OR=3.4; CI=1.7 to 7.1; $p<0.05$). Obesity (Adj. OR= 3.2; CI=1.9 to 6.0; $p<0.05$) and overweight (Adj. OR=2.3; CI=1.1 to 4.5; $p<0.05$) had shown significant impact on Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. Matric passed drivers (Adj. OR= 10.3; CI= 5.5 to 19.6; $p<0.05$) show higher level of Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders (Adj. OR= 0.15; CI= 0.052 to 0.39; $p<0.05$), followed by above 10+2 passed (Adj. OR= 1.8; CI= 0.70 to 4.3; $p<0.05$) and 10+2 passed (Adj. OR= 1.1; CI= 0.52 to

2.14; $p<0.05$). The odds of suffering from gastrointestinal disorders are also higher among drivers having family size above 6 members (Adj. OR=5.4; CI= 2.6 to 11.5; $p<0.05$) took less refreshment drinking/snacks during the day (≤ 2 Times) (Adj. OR= 5.7; CI= 3.5 to 9.5; $p<0.05$), consume main meal from dhabas / restaurants (Adj. OR=5.7; CI= 3.4 to 9.5; $p<0.05$), having vegan dietary habits (Adj. OR= 4.8; CI= 2.9 to 7.8; $p<0.05$), consumed of oily, fried items and junk food (Adj. OR= 7.6; CI= 4.6 to 13.0; $p<0.05$) and had lack of time for physical exercise/morning walk/ evening walk (Adj. OR= 1.8; CI= 1.1 to 2.7; $p<0.05$). Regular consumption of alcohol (Adj. OR=8.6; CI=4.8 to 15.8; $p<0.05$), habitual smokers (Adj. OR= 7.2; CI= 4.2 to 12.4; $p<0.05$), consumption of tobacco (Adj. OR= 3.2; CI= 1.9 to 5.5; $p<0.05$) and drugs intake (sleep inhibitors) (Adj. OR= 4.8; CI= 2.8 to 8.2; $p<0.05$) had significant impact on Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. However, drivers who took meal at a proper and fixed time (Adj. OR= 0.22; CI= 0.13 to 0.36; $p<0.05$) are less likely to suffer from Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders as compared to their reference category.

From the above findings it can be concluded that the socio-demographic factors which increases the prevalence of odds of Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders are higher age, higher BMI (obesity), low level of education, large family size, short sleep duration, less refreshment drinking/snacks during the day, consumption of main meal from dhabas/restaurants, dietary habits (mixed diet), consumption of oily, fried items and junk food, little physical exercise/morning walk/ evening walk, intake of alcohol, smoking, tobacco and drugs (sleep inhibitors).

Table 3

Association of Socio -Demographic & Life Style Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Factors	N	Yes (n)	No (n)	X2 (coefficient)	p	Df	Adj. OR	CI (95%)	
Age	Up to 30 years	72	42	30	53.267(0.388)	0.000*	3	1	
	31-40 years	78	49	29				0.83	0.43-1.60
	41-50	66	19	47				3.4	1.7-7.1
	Above 50Years	84	12	72				8.4	3.9-18.1
BMI(kg/m2)	Under weight	90	49	41	22.208 (0.263)	0.000*	3	1	
	Normal	42	24	18				0.89	0.42-1.87
	Over weight	54	19	35				2.3	1.1-4.5
	Obesity	114	30	84				3.3	1.9-6.0
Education	Below Matric	96	61	35	68.930 (0.432)	0.000*	5	1	
	Matric	132	19	113				10.3	5.5-19.6
	10+2	48	30	18				1.1	0.52-2.14
	Above 10+2 (Graduation, Technical and Diploma/Certificate	24	12	12					

Family Size (Members)	Up to 2	48	13	35	59.793 (0.408)	0.000*	3	1	1	
	3-4	78	55	23				0.39		0.20-0.73
	5-6	90	43	47				2.8		1.3-5.9
	Above 6	84	12	72				5.4		2.6-11.5
Sleep	≤6 Hours	120	24	96	35.402 (0.325)	0.000*	1	4.8	2.8-8.2	
	>6 Hours	180	98	82				1		1
Refreshment drinking/snacks during the day	≤2 Times	180	44	136	49.079 (0.375)	0.000*	1	5.7	3.5-9.5	
	>2 Times	120	78	42				1		1
Main meal from	Regularly	192	50	142	47.277 (0.369)	0.000*	1	5.7	3.4-9.5	
Dhabas /Restaurants	Occasionally	108	72	36			1			1
Dietary Habits	Mixed diet	174	44	130	40.610 (0.345)	0.000*		4.8	2.9-7.8	
	Vegan	126	78	48				1		1
Consumption of oily, fried items and junk food	On most of the days	174	37	137	64.635 (0.421)	0.000*	1	7.6	4.6-13.0	
	Occasionally	126	85	41				1		1
Take meal at proper and fixed time	Yes	114	72	42	38.548 (0.337)	0.000*	1	0.22	0.13-0.36	
	No	186	50	136				1		1
Get time for physical exercise/morning walk/ evening walk	Never/ Sometimes	174	61	113	5.402 (0.133)	0.000*	1	1.8	1.1-2.7	
	Often/ Very Frequent	126	61	65				1		1
Alcohol	Yes	222	62	160	57.424 (0.401)	0.000*	1	8.6	4.8-15.8	
	No	78	60	18				1		1
Smoking	Yes	138	24	114	57.377 (0.401)	0.000*	1	7.2	4.2-12.4	
	No	162	98	64				1		1
Tobacco	Yes	222	74	148	19.030 (0.244)	0.000*	3.2	1.9-5.5		
	No	78	48	30			1		1	
Drugs (sleep inhibitors)	Yes	120	24	96	35.402 (0.325)	0.000*	1	4.8	2.8-8.2	
	No	180	98	82				1		1

Note. Source: Primary Data compiled through survey using SPSS; $p=0.05$; * $p < 0.05$ (Significant); $p > 0.050$ (Not significant); Adj. OR=Adjusted Odds Ratio; I=Reference Category; CI=Class Interval

Association of Work-related Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Table 4 presents the level of associations between work-related factors and Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. The analysis reveals that drivers having driving experience above 20 years (Adj. OR= 16.4; CI=7.2 to 37.6; $p < 0.05$) followed by 16-20 years (Adj. OR=4.3; CI=1.9 to 9.5; $p < 0.05$) and 6-10 years (Adj. OR=2.8; CI=1.3 to 5.4; $p < 0.05$), having monthly income Rs. 5000-8000 (Adj. OR= 2.5; CI= 0.32 to 21.0; $p < 0.05$), Working for more than ten days consecutively without a holiday (Adj. OR= 3.4; CI= 2.1 to 5.7; $p < 0.05$), drove taxi more than 5 hours without taking any rest (Adj.

OR= 4.1; CI= 2.5 to 6.8; $p < 0.05$), drove taxi up to 16 hours per day (Adj. OR= 9.8; CI= 4.6 to 21.0; $p < 0.05$), drove more mileage (Adj. OR=2.5; CI=1.6 to 4.0; $p < 0.05$) and suffered from fatigue (Adj. OR= 4.2; CI= 2.5 to 6.8; $p < 0.05$) are more at risk of suffer from Gastrointestinal Diseases. So, it is crystal clear that all variables contribute significantly to Gastrointestinal Diseases. Results shows that there is a significant impact of work-related factors i.e. job experience, monthly income, working for more than ten days consecutively without a holiday for a whole day intervening, driving a taxi more than 5 hours without any rest, more work duration, more mileage and fatigue on Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders.

Table 4

Association of Work Related Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Factors	N	Yes (n)	No (n)	X2 (coefficient)	p	Df	Adj. OR	CI (95%)	
Job experience	6-10 Years	102	49	53	54.261 (0.391)	0.000*	3	1	
	11-15 Years	60	43	17				2.8	1.3-5.4
	16-20 Years	48	18	30				4.3	1.9-9.5
	Above 20 Years	90	12	78				16.4	7.2-37.6
Monthly Income	Below 3000	126	24	102	54.906 (0.393)	0.000*	3	1	
	3000-5000	150	91	59				0.16	0.09-0.27
	5000-8000	12	1	11				2.5	0.32-21.0
	Above 8000	12	6	6				0.23	0.07-0.80

Work for more than ten days consecutively without a holiday for a whole day intervening	Yes	210	67	143	22.272 (0.263)	0.000*	1	3.4	2.1-5.7
	No	90	55	35				1	1
Drive taxi more than 5 hours without taking any rest	Yes	204	61	143	29.238 (0.304)	0.000*	1	4.1	2.5-6.8
	No	96	61	35				1	1
Work Duration	Up to 8 hours	72	42	30	60.750 (0.410)	0.000*	3	1	1
	Up to 12 hours	90	56	34				0.85	0.45-1.60
	Up to 16 hours	96	12	84				9.8	4.6-21.0
	Above 16 hours	42	12	30				3.5	1.6-7.9
Total Mileage	Yes	174	55	119	14.086 (0.121)	0.000*	1	2.5	1.6-4.0
	No	126	67	59				1	1
Fatigue	Often/ Very Frequent	132	30	102	31.439 (0.038)	0.000*	1	4.2	2.5-6.8
	Never/ Sometimes	168	92	76				1	1

Note. Source: Primary Data complied through survey using SPSS; $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.05$ (Significant); $p > 0.050$ (Not significant); Adj. OR=Adjusted Odds Ratio; 1=Reference Category; CI=Class Interval

Association of Ergonomics Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Table 5 shows the results of Chi Square Test to find the relationship of Ergonomics Factors with Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. The result reveals that there is significant association of Ergonomics Factors with Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. The analysis reveals that the taxi drivers who handle baggages and materials (Adj. OR=3.2; CI=1.8 to 5.5; $p < 0.05$), indulge in bending and twisting activities while driving (Adj. OR=3.3; CI=2.0 to 5.7; $p < 0.05$), experienced violence (victim of assault) during working hours (Adj. OR=3.8; CI=2.2 to 6.0; $p < 0.05$), drive in too much cold and hot weather (Adj. OR=6.3; CI=3.6 to 10.7; $p < 0.05$), sleep on the taxi seat during rest breaks (Adj. OR=4.8; CI=2.9 to 7.8; $p < 0.05$) are more at risk of suffer from Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. Data further reveals that other Ergonomics Factors which associated with Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders are narrow cabin space (Adj. OR=2.8; CI=1.6 to 5.1; $p < 0.05$), longer working hours (Adj. OR=4.8; CI=2.8 to 7.9; $p < 0.05$), driving on heavy traffic roads/traffic congestion (Adj. OR=4.2; CI=2.5 to 6.8; $p < 0.05$), frequent driver seat vibration (Adj. OR=3.4; CI=1.9 to 2.9; $p < 0.05$), poor design of seat (Adj. OR=2.5; CI=1.6 to 4.0; $p < 0.05$), lack of awareness of good sitting posture (Adj. OR=4.5; CI=2.7 to 7.4; $p < 0.05$), uncomfortable steering wheel (Adj. OR=3.1; CI=2.0 to 5.2;

$p < 0.05$), uncomfortable seat (Adj. OR=2.3; CI=1.4 to 3.9; $p < 0.05$), uncomfortable back support (Adj. OR=4.8; CI=2.9 to 7.8; $p < 0.05$), inadequate rest period during the working days (Adj. OR=3.0; CI=1.8 to 4.8; $p < 0.05$), lack of accessibility to the lavatory (Adj. OR=1.4; CI=0.90 to 2.3; $p < 0.05$), seat inclination (seat pan) (Adj. OR=7.6; CI=4.5 to 12.9; $p < 0.05$), sitting without lumbar support (Adj. OR=3.1; CI=2.0 to 5.2; $p < 0.05$) and shocks (due to poor road surface) (Adj. OR=6.0; CI=3.6 to 9.9; $p < 0.05$). These aforesaid factors are found important Ergonomics Factors which significantly increase the odds of Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. Since the findings of the study further reveals that Ergonomics Factors that increased prevalence of Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders are handling of baggages and materials, bending and twisting activities while driving, experience of violence (victim of assault) during working hours, too much cold and hot weather, sleep on the taxi seat during rest breaks, small cabin space, increased work pace/high work load, driving in heavy traffic/traffic contestation, greater driver seat vibration, design and cushions of seat, poor /low awareness of good sitting posture, uncomfortable steering wheel, uncomfortable seat, uncomfortable back support, inadequate rest period during the working day, lack of accessibility to the lavatory, poor seat inclination (seat pan), sitting without lumbar support and shocks (due to road surface).

Table 5
Association of Ergonomics Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Factors	N	Yes (n)	No (n)	X2 (coefficient)	p	Df	Adj. OR	CI (95%)	
Handling baggage's and materials	Often/ Very Frequent	220	73	147	19.155 (0.245)	0.000*	1	3.2	1.8-5.5
	Never/Sometimes	80	49	31				1	1
Bending and twisting activities while driving	Often/Very Frequent	221	73	148	20.275 (0.252)	0.000*	1	3.3	2.0-5.7
	Never/Sometimes	79	49	30				1	1
Experience Violence (victim of assault) during working hours	Often/Very Frequent	174	48	126	29.377 (0.299)	0.000*	1	3.8	2.2-6.0
	Never/Sometimes	126	74	52				1	1
Too much cold and hot weather	Often/Very Frequent	204	55	149	49.631 (0.377)	0.000*	1	6.3	3.6-10.7
	Never/Sometimes	96	67	29				1	1
Sleep on the taxi seat during rest breaks	Never	126	44	130	40.610 (0.345)	0.000*	1	4.8	2.9-7.8
	Sometimes	174	78	48				1	1

Narrow cabin space	Yes	84	20	64	13.740 (0.209)	0.000*	1	2.8	1.6-5.1
	No	216	102	114				1	1
Longer working hours	Yes	144	32	112	39.044 (0.339)	0.000*	1	4.8	2.8-7.9
	No	156	90	66				1	1
Driving on heavy traffic roads/traffic congestion	Yes	132	30	102	31.439 (0.308)	0.000*	1	4.2	2.5-6.8
	No	168	92	76				1	1
Frequent driver seat vibration	Yes	90	20	70	18.128 (0.239)	0.000*	1	3.4	1.9-2.9
	No	210	102	108				1	1
Poor design of seat	Yes	174	55	119	14.086 (0.212)	0.000*	1	2.5	1.6-4.0
	No	126	67	59				1	1
Lack of awareness of good sitting posture	Yes	138	31	107	35.094 (0.324)	0.000*	1	4.5	2.7-7.4
	No	162	91	71				1	1
Uncomfortable steering wheel	Yes	186	56	130	22.618 (0.265)	0.000*	1	3.1	2.0-5.2
	No	114	66	48				1	1
Uncomfortable seat	Yes	108	30	78	11.618 (0.193)	0.000*	1	2.3	1.4-3.9
	No	192	92	100				1	1
Uncomfortable back support	Yes	174	44	130	40.610 (0.345)	0.000*	1	4.8	2.9-7.8
	No	126	78	48				1	1
Inadequate rest period during the working day	Yes	150	42	108	19.948 (0.250)	0.000*	1	3.0	1.8-4.8
	No	150	80	70				1	1
Lack of accessibility to the lavatory	Yes	180	67	113	2.213 (0.086)	0.000*	1	1.4	0.90-2.3
	No	120	55	65				1	1
Seat inclination (Seat Pan)	Yes	162	32	130	63.838 (0.419)	0.000*	1	7.6	4.5-12.9
	No	138	90	48				1	1
Sitting without lumbar support	Yes	186	56	130	22.618 (0.265)	0.000*	1	3.1	2.0-5.2
	No	114	66	48				1	1
Shocks (due to road surface)	Yes	150	31	119	49.733 (0.377)	0.000*	1	6.0	3.6-9.9
	No	150	91	59				1	1

Note. Source: Primary Data compiled through survey using SPSS; $p=0.05$; * $p < 0.05$ (Significant); $p > 0.050$ (Not significant); Adj. OR=Adjusted Odds Ratio; 1=Reference Category; CI=Class Interval

Association of Psychological Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Table 6 shows the association between Psychological Factors and Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders on the basis of Chi-Square values. Chi Square value reveals ($p < 0.05$) that there is an association between Psychological Factors and Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. The study reveals that self perceived stress/stress symptoms (Adj. OR=12.0; CI=6.0 to 21.0; $p < 0.05$), exposure to passenger hostility (Adj. OR=4.0; CI=2.5 to 6.6; $p < 0.05$) and too

short lunch break (Adj. OR=3.1; CI=1.9 to 5.3; $p < 0.05$) are among the major risk factors of gastrointestinal disorders. Taxi drivers who reported the aforementioned psychological problems were found more likely to suffer from Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders. However, the level of social contact with colleagues and lack of social support (Adj. OR=0.86; CI=0.54 to 1.4; $p < 0.05$) are not found significant to have any significant impact on Gastrointestinal Diseases. The psychological factors that contribute to the Gastrointestinal Diseases/Disorders are self-perceived stress/stress symptoms, exposure to passenger hostility and too short lunch break.

Table 6

Association of Psychological Factors with Gastrointestinal Disorders

Factors	N	Yes (n)	No (n)	X ² (coefficient)	p	Df	Adj. OR	CI (95%)	
Self perceived stress/ Stress symptoms	Yes	162	26	136	88.450 (0.477)	0.000*	1	12.0	6.9-21.0
	No	138	96	42				1	1
Exposure to passenger hostility	Yes	150	37	113	31.829 (0.310)	0.000*	1	4.0	2.5-6.6
	No	150	85	65				1	1
Level of social contact with colleagues and lack of Social Support	Never/ Sometimes	186	49	65	0.409 (0.037)	0.000*	1	0.86	0.54-1.4
	Often/ Very Frequent	114	73	113				1	1
Lunch break too short	Yes	120	30	90	20.344 (0.252)	0.000*	1	3.1	1.9-5.3
	No	180	92	88				1	1

Note. Source: Primary Data compiled through survey using SPSS; $p=0.05$; * $p < 0.05$ (Significant); $p > 0.050$ (Not significant); Adj. OR=Adjusted Odds Ratio; 1=Reference Category; CI=Class Interval

On the basis of results of Multiple Logistic Regression a model has been developed which is consonance with Hypothesized Model (Figure 1) and proved that various risk factors taken in the study has significant impact on the Gastrointestinal Disorders.

Figure 1

Impact of Various Stress Related Risk Factors on Gastrointestinal Disorders

Discussion

The gastrointestinal tract is a series of hollow organs that form a long continuous passage from our mouth to our anus. The organs that make up our GI tract are our mouth, esophagus, stomach, small intestine, large intestine, and anus when we do not take care of these organs it creates gastrointestinal disorders. The analysis of data reveals that null hypotheses have been rejected and findings of study reveal that the risk factors considered in this study has significant impact on various stress related health problems of taxi drivers. It implies that more exposure to these risk factors, namely, life style, work related, psychological, ergonomics, working conditions and other diseases experienced by taxi drivers for a long duration lead to problems like gastrointestinal disorder (Bartone, 1989; David et al., 1988; Evans, 1994; Hedberg, 1985; Netterstrøm & Juel, 1990; Netterstrøm & Sudicani, 1989; Tse et al., 2006; Van der Beek et al., 1994). In addition, numerous studies outside of India show that compared to other occupational groups, transport workers-particularly drivers-are more likely to suffer from gastrointestinal (GI) illnesses (Bartone, 1989; Beek et al., 1994; Netterstrøm & Juel, 1990). Long periods of sitting, irregular eating, and psychological stress are major contributors to digestive symptoms among bus and taxi drivers, according to research from Germany and Denmark

(Netterstrom, 1989). According to a cross-national research by Tse et al. (2006), gastrointestinal disorders are among the most prevalent physical health issues among drivers and are frequently linked to shift work and unfavorable ergonomic conditions (Tse et al., 2006). According to research from Scandinavia, professional drivers were more likely to experience dyspepsia and peptic ulcers as a result of work-related stress, irregular eating patterns, and a lack of rest periods (David et al., 1988; Backman, 1983). Furthermore, research has highlighted that although drivers frequently acknowledge their health issues, they frequently put their own health last because of demanding work schedules and financial strains (Tse et al., 2006; Evans, 1994). These global results corroborate our findings that a combination of work-related stress, erratic lifestyles, and restricted access to preventive healthcare services may be responsible for GI problems among Indian taxi drivers.

The study highlights that taxi drivers are more likely to experience gastrointestinal disorders than non-professional drivers. Professional taxi drivers have a life style that is not congenial and conducive to good health along with exposure to air and noise pollution. Their job does not provide more opportunities for social contact as many other jobs, and long unsocial working hours and shift work etc., can interrupt both home life and social life. Home life and social contacts with friends and relatives provide a powerful source of psychological support for those experiencing stress and an absence of social support multiples an already complex problem. Taxi drivers are more likely to have a diet that is not favourable to health than those workers who can return home for an evening meal and take regular meal breaks in a staff canteen on a regular basis. A diet high in carbohydrates and fats and low in fresh food, fruit, salads vegetables, and fibre will contribute to the level of unhygienic and poor health. The incidence of drinking and smoking can also produce health problems and most empirical studies on drivers provide a strong basis to "control" for this important aspect of life style. Drivers are victims of these diseases because they smoke and drink a lot. Drivers are exposed to many health problems as a direct result of the seat and posture adopted while on wheel. Sitting in the driving position exerts significant force on the spine and can cause a number of problems with the musculoskeletal system particularly in backaches, neck problems, pulled muscles, and general stiffness. The drivers' life style and driving posture also creates many problems for the digestive system.

Recommendations, Implications and Scope for Future Research

Recommendations for Government

- The Government of Punjab should provide basic amenities and services to satisfy the transport workers. Taxi owners should provide a healthy and safe environment.
- There should be effective and strict implementation of provisions of the Cigarette and other Tobacco Products Act (COTPA) and anti-alcohol laws.
- It has been observed that the workers of countries with a higher literacy rate have better health related knowledge. Therefore, the government should take steps to raise the level of literacy of the transport workers to make them aware of the Labour Legislations and Health Schemes. The study found that a majority of the illiterate workers fail to take advantage of the Labour Legislations, MTWA, 1961 and Health Schemes due to a lack of awareness.

Recommendations for Society

- Quality of Work Life (QWL) is a shared responsibility not only by the taxi owners and government but also by society (Passengers & police etc.).
- It is recommended that doctors familiarize taxi drivers with the risk of sedation while prescribing antihistamines. Therefore, the doctor should suggest the patients stop driving after taking any antihistamine.

Recommendations for Taxi Owners

- Taxi owners need to work and cooperate with researchers, policy makers, trade unions, and taxi drivers, to take initiatives that safeguard and protect drivers against occupational stress.
- The study also suggests that each owner should frame their tour and trip plans according to the availability of taxis and taxi drivers, so that additional burden of overwork of taxi drivers could be reduced.
- Taxi owners should promote health education and regular mental check-ups and periodical physical examination to identify and manage such risk factors that lead to stress related health problems.
- Working hours of taxi drivers should be rationalized as per the standard norms.
- Occupational Health and Safety training should be developed for drivers to avoid the adverse effects of occupational risk factors on drivers' health. The study further recommends that the reduction of driving time to lessen the duration of whole-body vibration (WBV) exposure should also be considered by the taxi owners.

Recommendations for Taxi Drivers

- Taxi drivers should avoid smoking and alcohol while driving.
- Leisure time activities and weekly offs to taxi drivers can act as a stress buster.
- Taxi drivers should be advised to take breaks to take rest during working hours so that accident rates can be reduced.
- Strategies for better health may include getting adequate sleep before driving. Drivers should wash their hands frequently, eat healthy snacks and take frequent stretch breaks to address nutritional inactivity and concerns.
- Overweight and obesity are an arena of multiple health problems so drivers should control their body weight (Body Mass Index) through regular and habitual physical exercise.
- In view of the behaviours evidenced in the present research, it is recommended that changes in routine habits must be stimulated and characterised by regular physical activity, control of body weight and abstinence from alcohol, tobacco and smoking to reduce the potential risk of stress related problems.
- Taxi drivers should avoid breathing in exhaust gases and fumes and other pollutants when standing near vehicles and switch off the engine when not required and when parked.

Implications of the Study

Implications of the Study for Policy Makers

- The findings of this study will be useful for the HR managers and Government, Policy Makers particularly the Ministry of Labour and Welfare, and all those who are concerned with the health and safety and life of professional drivers.
- The results of present study would help to strengthen and support

the database of common morbidities which need attention among the professional drivers and would serve as an impetus and force for designing favourable job policies for drivers.

Implications of the Study for Professional Drivers

- The results of the study found that taxi drivers are using various Central Nervous Agents (CNAs). So, the present study will help them to be aware of the negative impact of CNAs and the positive impact of a healthy life style, hygienic eating habits, sound sleeping, and exercise and physical fitness.
- It will help the professional drivers, especially engaged in long distance driving to identify their health-related issues and their causes and help them to be aware of health-related problems and remedies.
- Some taxi drivers still prefer to work under the pressure of taxi owners due to lack of awareness of the Motor Transport Workers Act, 1961 and lack of job security concerns. The findings of the study will motivate taxi drivers to follow the provisions of this act, to demand the implementation of the various provisions of the act.

Scope for Further Research

Several issues, associated with the limitations inherent in this study, create scope for further research:

- Longitudinal studies are required to confirm the examined cross-sectional association and to further observe the specific occupational exposures responsible for the association between driving time and stress related problems, such as Hypertension, Cardiovascular, Gastrointestinal and Musculoskeletal Disorders.
- Similar studies may be performed by increasing sample size and involving more refined expertise and techniques to yield better outcomes.
- Findings of the present study may be tested by conducting similar studies. Further study may be conducted on impact of dietary habits on drivers' health and lifestyle factors.
- Blood samples may be collected in plain tubes for blood examination to check the hemoglobin levels, blood sugar levels, and complete blood profile and thyroid status.
- The World Health Organization step-wise approach may be used in the future to determine the magnitude of cardiovascular risk factors, e.g., anthropometric measurements along with a questionnaire-based survey to study behavioral risk factors.
- Standard procedures and instruments might be used for anthropometric measurements. Standard tape for height measurement, standard balance for measurement and standard mercury sphygmomanometer (appropriately maintained & calibrated) for blood pressure measurement might be used.
- Further, research may be conducted by measuring the abdominal circumference which correlates better with Hypertension than Body Mass Index.

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